

MITRAL VALVE PROLAPSE IN CHILDREN: CLINICAL, FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

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Relevance. In the structure of cardiovascular pathology, functional disorders and conditions associated with minor anomalies of heart development are of great importance. In 96-99% of cases, they are not detected during examination, remain undiagnosed, or are detected by chance during examination for another pathology. Mitral valve prolapse (MVP) is a pathological sagging (bending) of one or both mitral valve leaflets into the left atrium during left ventricular systole.

Purpose of the study. To study the clinical and functional features of the cardiovascular system in children with mitral valve prolapse.

Materials and methods of research. The study included 30 children with mitral valve prolapse aged from 1 month to 5 years. The control group consisted of 20 children without MVP. The children were examined at the City Children's Medical Consultative Diagnostic Center. The study used general clinical, biochemical, functional, instrumental and statistical methods.

Research results. The distribution of children with MVP by age showed that they were less common in children aged 1 month to 1 year (26.7%) and more common in children aged 2 to 5 years (73.3%). During the study of medical and biological factors in children with MVP, it was shown that MVP develops more often in boys (56.7%). The development of MVP was more prevalent in children with hereditary burden (26.6%). In 16.6% of children, the mother's age was over 35 years at the time of the birth of this child, and in 10.0% of children, the parents were close relatives. Obstetric history data showed that mothers of children with MVP suffered ARVI during pregnancy in 50.0% of cases, and TORCH infections (cytomegalovirus, herpes virus) were detected in 20.0% of cases. The study of physical development indicators of children with MVP also did not reveal deviations in body length/height, body weight and body mass index relative to age norms. Physical examination showed that, upon percussion, in 3 (7.5%) children there was an expansion of the left boundaries of relative

cardiac dullness. Auscultation revealed a systolic click at the apex of the heart with a late systolic murmur in 30 (100%) children. Analysis of the ECG study showed that (10%) children had signs of hypertrophy of the left stomach; among conduction disorders, incomplete blockade of the left bundle branch in (26.6%) and early repolarization syndrome prevailed in (23.3%) children. Among heart rhythm disturbances, such as sinus tachycardia and sinus bradycardia were noted in equal percentages in (6.6%) children. EchoCG data shows that in children with MVP, the contractility of the LV is preserved, and the size of the left ventricle is not changed. Only 10% of children with MVP had dilatation of the left chambers of the heart due to stage III regurgitation of the mitral valve. Thus, when studying the clinical and functional features of MVP in the left ventricle in children, it was shown that, with MVP, the structural and geometric parameters of the heart chambers of the left ventricle and the disruption of their function do not change depending on the degree of mitral valve prolapse.

References:

1. Ахрарова Ф.М. Клинико-патогенетическое обоснование формирования сердечно - сосудистой патологии у детей с кардиальными проявлениями дисплазии соединительной ткани автореф. дис. кандидат мед. наук: 14.00.09 / Ахрарова Ф.М. – СПб., 2020. – 20 с.
2. Гольденберг А. Е., Денисова Т. В., Бугун О. В. Распространенность малых аномалий развития сердца у детей, проживающих в различных экологических зонах (результаты эхокардиографического скрининга) // Вестник аритмологии. 2018. Т. 39, № 1. С. 124.
3. Земцовский Э.В. Малые аномалии сердца: попытка ревизии рабочей классификации с позиций кардиолога-клинициста / Э.В. Земцовский Э.Г. Малев. //Бюллетень федерального центра сердца, крови и эндокринологии им. В. А. Алмазова. – 2019. - №4. - С. 67-73.
4. Меншикова Л.И. Дисплазия соединительной ткани сердца в генезе кардиоваскулярной патологии у детей / Л.И. Меншикова, О.В. Сурова //Вестник аритмологии – 2018. – №19. -С.54-59.
5. Мухсинова М.Х. Малые аномалии сердца у детей (обзор литературы). / Мухсинова М.Х., Хужаева Ф. С., Абдувохидов Ж.З. // Re-health journal. - 2021. - №2(10). С. 173-181.
6. Caselli S., Mango F., Clark J. et al. Prevalence and Clinical Outcome of Athletes With Mitral Valve Prolapse. *Circulation*, 2018, vol. 137, pp. 2080–2082.
7. Corrado D., Basso C., Nava A. et al. Sudden death in young people with apparently isolated mitral valve prolapse // *G. Ital Cardiol*. 2018. Vol. 27. P. 1097–1105.

8. Daliendo L. Mitral valvar prolapse: overlap or masked syndrome? / *Cardiol Young*, 2019, vol. 12, pp. 317–319.
9. Finocchiaro G., Papadakis M., Robertus J.-L. et al. Etiology of sudden death in sports. Insights from a United Kingdom regional registry. *Jour Am Coll Cardiol.*, 2018, vol. 67, no. 18, pp. 2108–2115.
10. Muxsinova M.X. Bolalardagi kichik yurak anomaliylarining klinik va funktsional xususiyatlari. / Muxsinova M.X., Ortikov U.U., Xujaeva F., Abduvohidov J.Z., Abdurazakova Z.K. // *Евразийский вестник педиатрии*. 2021. - №3(10). - С.98-104.

